

Development of an IOT Based 3D printer

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ABSTRACT

Now a days 3D printing technology is evolving in all sectors. In the present work, a 3D printer based on Internet of Things (IOT) was developed. The main objective of the project was to develop an affordable 3D printer in low cost and to use IOT technology for remote monitoring, control, and maintenance of the printer. A comparative study was carried between the solid 3D printed parts and hollow 3D printed parts filled with expandable foams. Expandable foam is a versatile material that expands upon application to fill gaps, cracks, or voids. It typically starts as a liquid or semi-liquid substance contained in a pressurized container. When dispensed, it reacts with moisture in the air to expand and solidify into a foam. It was noticed that, hollow 3D printed parts filled with expandable foams possess higher strength than the solid 3D printed parts.

Keywords: Internet of Things, 3D printing, Additive Manufacturing, expandable foams.

1. Introduction

3D printer uses many layers of material to create 3D objects and parts. It is a mechanized process in which the parts are produced according to the required shape and size. A computer aided design (CAD) model is used to print the material. A computer which is connected to the 3D printer machine controls the printing process. 3D printing generally called as additive manufacturing comprise of Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM), stereolithography (SL), Laser sintering (LS), high speed sintering (HSS). In the earlier days 3D printing techniques were used for aesthetic prototypes, but in recent days the application of 3D printing techniques has covered various sectors and a wide variety of products including complex geometries to hollow parts can be produced.

3D printing has gained importance in manufacturing sector due its many benefits like design freedom, capability to produce complex shapes compared to traditional methods of manufacturing, reduced cost, and acceptability. 3D printing process starts with creating a CAD model with the help of CAD software packages. Followed by CAD models are saved in stereolithography (STL) format. Later slicing up of a 3D model into hundreds or thousands of layers is carried out with slicing software. At last, feeding the sliced file to printer to initiate printing process.

Internet of Things (IoT) refers to the network of interconnected devices that communicate and exchange data with each other over the internet, without requiring human intervention. These devices can range from everyday objects like household appliances and wearable gadgets to industrial machines and sensors. The key idea is to enable these devices to collect, transmit, and analyze data to automate tasks, improve efficiency, and enhance decision-making processes

2. Literature

Additive Manufacturing has gained significant attention from researchers all over the world to develop light weight and complicated structures. Sum of them explained about rate of deposition, rate of cooling.

Fujii et al [1] reported fused filament fabrication (FFF) 3D printers have the advantages of being able to build complex structures automatically and at low cost. On the other hand, the tensile strength in the thickness direction is lower than that in the horizontal direction for objects fabricated by using fused filament fabrication 3D printers. In this study, we conducted mechanical evaluations by using an automatic strengthening method in which carbon-fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRPs) were embedded in the vertical direction in the form of joints, through 3D finite element method (FEM) simulations and experiments. We performed 3D FEM simulations on an analytical model with epoxy resin and two CFRP joints embedded inside polylactic acid, and confirmed that fracture occurred at the ends of the CFRP. The simulations showed that longer joint lengths and shorter distances between CFRPs increased the strength. Tensile testing of the specimens with CFRP embedded in the form of two CFRP joints showed that the maximum CFRP spacing affected the strength. This is consistent with the analysis results, which showed that the strength decreased with increasing CFRP spacing.

Wilson et al [2] reported that, the usage of 3d printing has been a widely applicable in various branches such as aerospace, medical, food industry and recently even in construction of houses. As we can see 3d printing has become a revolutionary invention and is becoming very common in manufacturing of various machining parts. So as we know there are various forms of 3d printing technologies and each of them have their own advantages and disadvantages. One of the main disadvantages is the quality of finishing on the 3d printed parts. Apart from this the cost of 3d printing has also been one of the major disadvantages. The purpose of this projects is to design and fabricate a 3d printer which would increase the quality of the parts manufactured and make it cost efficient. This quality product can be achieved by decreasing the layer thickness. The other ways to increase quality of the product is fabricate the 3d printer in such a way that the temperature of the nozzle is within the given range all through the process. This project is expected to result in the fabrication of the 3d printer considering all the above features.

Demircan et al [3] reported that, the technique of additive manufacturing has increasing popularity in food research area as well as other scientific fields. However, 3D food printers are expensive options compared to 3D polymer printers. Scientists, that require laboratory scale production capacities, resemble the syringe-pump systems that available in open source and free hardware designs. Present study aimed to develop an exchangeable syringe-pump mechanism (SPM) to demonstrate transformation of conventional 3D printer from polymer to food extrusion. The SPM can print a variety of materials, including miscellaneous foods, pastes, hydrogels and even biopolymers. The complete mechanism relies mostly on 3D printed parts and costs approximately 72\$. Therefore, it allows users to obtain a 3D food printer inexpensively and does not require large amounts of technical labour.

Lambos et al [4] reported the automated recognition of clogging in the nozzle of a typical material extrusion 3D printer, a fault that has potentially severe consequences for both the printer and the printed part, should it not be rectified in a timely manner. Several methods were considered initially, such as monitoring temperature or vibrations at low-cost, but they were ineffective for different reasons explained. Thus, an automated monitoring system was devised to analyze the acoustic signals generated by driver gear's slippage on the filament during the blocking phase. Instead of Fast Fourier spectrum-based solutions which were unreliable, the Goertzel algorithm was used. Thus, the unique frequency of the sound emitted under clogging conditions previously identified is detected fast enough for real time response with a low-cost microcontroller. The algorithm was proved to be reliable through experimental testing performed on a typical 3D printer of the material extrusion type.

Baier et al [5] Additive manufacturing encompasses a plethora of techniques to manufacture structures from a computational model. Among them, fused filament fabrication (FFF) relies on heating thermoplastics to their fusion point and extruding the material through a nozzle in a controlled pattern. FFF is a suitable technique for tissue engineering, given that allows the fabrication of 3D-scaffolds, which are utilized for tissue regeneration purposes. The objective of this study is to assess a low-cost/open-source 3D printer (In-House), by manufacturing both solid and porous samples with relevant microarchitecture in the physiological range (100–500 μm pore size), using an equivalent commercial counterpart for comparison. For this, compressive tests in solid and porous scaffolds manufactured in both printers were performed, comparing the results with finite element analysis (FEA) models. Additionally, a microarchitectural analysis was done in samples from both printers, comparing the measurements of both pore size and porosity to their corresponding computer-aided design (CAD) models. Moreover, a preliminary biological assessment was performed using scaffolds from our In-House printer, measuring cell adhesion efficiency. Finally, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy – attenuated total reflectance (FTIR–ATR) was performed to evaluate chemical changes in the material (polylactic acid) after fabrication in each printer. The results show that the In-House printer achieved generally better mechanical behavior and resolution capacity than its commercial counterpart, by comparing with their FEA and CAD models, respectively. Moreover, a preliminary biological assessment indicates the feasibility of the In-House printer to be used in tissue engineering applications..

Buswell et al [6] Large-scale additive manufacturing processes for construction utilise computer-controlled placement of extruded cement-based mortar to create physical objects layer-by-layer. Demonstrated applications include component manufacture and placement of in-situ walls for buildings. These applications vary the constraints on design parameters and present different technical issues for the production process. In this paper, published and new work are utilized to explore the relationship between fresh and hardened paste, mortar, and concrete material properties and how they influence the geometry of the created object. Findings are classified by construction application to create a matrix of issues that identifies the spectrum of future research exploration in this emerging field.

3. Experimental Procedure

3D model of the printer is created using CAD package as shown in Figure 1. Based on the 3D model, different parts needed to complete the 3D printer is selected. RAMPS is a board the serves as the interface between the Arduino mega, controller computer and the electronic devices on the 3D printer. The computer extracts information from files containing data about the object need to be printed and translates it into digital codes. It organizes and amplifies the information coming from the Arduino mega so that they are properly directed down to the correct channels.

Figure 1. 3D model of the printer

Arduino Mega is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega2560. It has 54 digital input/output pins (of which 14 can be used as PWM outputs), 16 analog inputs, 4 UARTs (hardware serial ports), a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It contains everything needed to support the microcontroller. A Nema 17 stepper motor has a faceplate size of 42 x 42 mm. Nema 17 high torque stepper motors offer excellent value without sacrificing quality. The 0.9° step angle version of the motor is more precise than the standard 1.8° version. These motors are designed to deliver maximum torque while minimizing vibration and audible noise. A variety of motor windings and stack lengths are readily available, or the motors can be customized to meet the needs of your machine.

The extruder is responsible for melting the filament and depositing it layer by layer to create the printed object. It includes a hot end, which heats the filament, and a nozzle, through which the molten filament is extruded. End stop is a kind of switch also known as mechanical end stops which are contact based manual switches that determine when an object is at the end of the axis path. It works using simple touch sensor that functions as a switch where the switch is touched by an object. It signals to the motherboard that the main object is at the end of the path.

Power supply are usually clunky metal boxes with a row of screw terminals or a bundle of wires at one end and a fan on the side. It receives upto the 110 to 240 volts from the wall and steps them down to a more reasonable 12 to 24 volts. The A4988 is a complete micro stepping motor driver with built in transistor for easy operation. It is designed to operate bipolar stepper motors in full, half, quarter, eighth, and sixteenth step modes, with an output drive capacity of up to 35 V and ± 2 A. The A4988 includes a fixed off-time current regulator which can operate in Slow or Mixed decay modes.

4. Results and Discussion

Printing process is achieved in the following steps. Creating the CAD model using CAD packages. Followed by creating STL file, An STL file is a raw, unstructured file containing only the surface geometry of the three-dimensional object. It is generated by CAD software at the end of modelling to describe the surface and shape of the 3D model.

Slicing is the process of transforming an STL file into G-code. G-code contains printer commands, slicing takes the STL file geometry data and creates a list of instructions the printer must follow to print the model. Slicing gives instructions to the printer based on nozzle size, filament and print profile, considering temperature range, speed, and extrusion type. Printing is the simplest step starts by loading the material. The only things to consider are filament type, filament supply, using the correct nozzle for the filament and temperature range and accurate calibration. In the case of fused filament fabrication (FFF) prints, it is not necessary to post-process them, unless painting is necessary. Models printed with an SLA (stereolithography) 3D printer often require curing with UV light to ensure optimal mechanical and visual characteristics.

Print head and extrusion system are responsible for heating and extruding the thermoplastic print material through a nozzle to form the part. Factors like nozzle size and extrusion speed impact the level of detail the printer can achieve, as well as its print speed. The print head and extrusion system deposits material onto the print bed. As a part prints, the motion system moves the bed in discrete, equal steps to form the layers of the part. The precision of the motors driving the Z motion system control the resolution and quality of the part as it is built up in the Z direction. The print gantry directly controls the X and Y motion of the print head. It is responsible for drawing the tool paths that create each layer. The rigidity of this gantry and the quality of the motors and sensors controlling it impact the precision and accuracy of a part in plane with the print bed.

An FFF 3D printer builds its parts in discrete slices called layers. 3D printing slicer takes an STL file, divides it into layers, then calculates and creates a tool path for each layer. At the beginning of each layer, the print bed is set at a given height and the gantry motion system moves the print head along the tool path as the extrusion system deposits material. Since a printer cannot extrude plastic into thin air without it collapsing, all parts of each layer must be connected to the layer below. While this is implicitly true for some parts, others have overhangs that require supports. Supports are an automatically generated sacrificial scaffold that come in a few different forms: peel away supports made from the same material as the part, soluble supports that dissolve in a bath after printing, or release layer supports that build a scaffold of part material with an intermediary layer of release material in-between the part and the support structure. Printers with a secondary material for supports use a second nozzle on the print head specifically for support material. The layer-by-layer nature of the 3D printing process causes 3D printed parts exhibit transverse isotropic material properties. While isotropic materials have uniform material properties in all directions, transverse isotropic materials have one set of properties along an axis and a different set on planes normal to that axis. This translates to 3D printed parts, which exhibit higher part strength on XY planes along the Z axis.

5. Conclusion

In the present work, Internet of Things based 3D printer was developed. The main objective of the project was to develop an affordable 3D printer in low cost and to use IOT technology for remote monitoring, control, and maintenance of the printer. A comparative study was carried between the solid 3D printed parts and hollow 3D printed parts filled with expandable foams. Expandable foam is a versatile material that expands upon application to fill gaps, cracks, or voids. It typically starts as a liquid or semi-liquid substance contained in a pressurized container. When dispensed, it reacts with moisture in the air to expand and solidify into a foam. It was noticed that, hollow 3D printed parts filled with expandable foams possess higher strength than the solid 3D printed parts.

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